

A Content Analysis of ‘My English Book’ of the First-Year Middle School in the Light of the Multiple Intelligences Theory

Case Study: Algerian Textbooks

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Abstract

This study aimed at investigating and analyzing the activities of ‘My English Book’ of the first-year middle school in the light of the Multiple Intelligences Theory MIT. The purpose of the study was to find out the extent to which My Book of English for the first middle school incorporate the MIT using content analysis. The sample of the study included the student’s textbook of the first grade in the middle school and twenty-one teachers who work with this book (Thirteen male and eight female EFL teachers from different middle schools). The results revealed that although the minister of education tried to incorporate the various recent teaching and learning theories and approaches, no reference was made to MIT.

Keywords: English Book, Middle School, Multiple Intelligences Theory, Algeria

Introduction

The tremendous amount of research done by both applied linguists and psychologists has provided the practitioners with new knowledge and better insights into how a foreign language can be best learned and acquired. Psycholinguistic research has yielded evidence that different people learn differently and employ different learning strategies depending on different factors like their cognitive structure, aptitude, experience, age and motivation of learning. Thus, the topic of intelligence has been hotly debated in psychology. Traditionally, intelligence is defined in terms of intelligence quotient (IQ) that measures a narrow range of verbal/ linguistic and logical/mathematical abilities a person has.

The Multiple Intelligences Theory and its Inclusive Pedagogy

The Multiple Intelligences Theory (MIT), was introduced to the world in 1983 by the American psychologist Howard Gardner through his book: *Frames of Mind*, it is one of the most recent approaches in the primary English language teaching methods. Intelligence is a concept explaining all intellectual powers people have, (Sttodar, 1956), this means; there are not just two ways to be intelligent, but many ways. Gardner defines it as the ability to solve problems and fashion products that are valued in a particular cultural setting or community (Gardner, 1993). He posits that we have eight intelligences which can be divided into three main groups: object-related intelligence,

which includes mathematics and logic; object-free intelligence, including music and language; and personal intelligence, or the psychological perception we have of ourselves and others, (Project, 1999).

Gardner drew on findings from evolutionary biology, anthropology, developmental and cognitive psychology, neuropsychology and psychometrics, (Gilmen, 1997). The eight intelligences proposed by Gardner are: visual/spatial, verbal/linguistic, musical/rhythmic, logical/mathematical, bodily/kinesthetic, interpersonal, intrapersonal and naturalistic. Although individuals possess all eight intelligences, each has its own particular mix of intelligences, with some dominating over others, but they are not fixed and can change over time.

MIT and Education

Though Gardner (2004) intends and expects his theory to find an audience in the field of psychology, where intelligence is a realm of study. MIT was welcomed and embraced by educators more than psychological researchers and theorists. Subsequently, Gardner has looked more closely at what the theory might mean of schooling practice. Gardner clarifies that:

Yet, given the mission of the Van Leer Foundation, it was clear that I needed to say something about the educational implications of MI theory. So, I surveyed the literature on education and in the concluding chapters touched on some educational implications of the theory. This decision turned out to be another crucial point because it was educators, rather than psychologists, who found the theory of most interest. (Gardener, 2004. P. 225)

MIT allows teachers to be conscious of their teaching strategies and students' distinct abilities and learning strengths which will, in turn, allow them to incorporate different learning types and teaching strategies in their particular curriculum. Gardner's MIT posits that students would learn better when teachers use different methods, exercises and activities to reach all students, not only those who excel at linguistic and logical intelligence.

The Algerian educational system has undergone fundamental changes during the last decades. Since it is at the heart of education, the English language curriculum taught at the Algerian schools has been affected by these changes too. The Algerian Ministry of National Education realizes the unquestionable importance of the English language as a global means of communication for those who wish to be part of the modern globalized world. It also realizes that learning English nowadays occupies a prominent position in today's technological world.

The ministry indicates that learning English enables students to cope with the vast changes and developments that take place around the world which is becoming a small village. Thus, in the light of the great need to improve the process of learning English as a foreign in Algeria, the Algerian English language teaching textbooks were changed several times to cope with the vast technological revolutions of the present era.

My Book of English is the book that is currently taught at schools in Algeria for year one of middle school. It is based on the most modern methods of learning

languages, combining a topic-based approach with functional language practice, careful attention to grammar and vocabulary and a comprehensive skills syllabus, (Lambert, 1996), it also covers language components and skills with a variety of activities that encourage communication and gradual development of students' knowledge. This book was introduced in the year 2006, it is interesting, colorful, and well-edited. My book of English covers language components and skills with varieties of activities.

The implications of the eight Intelligences for teaching/learning are enormous. Traditionally, Algerian educational institutions tend to focus mostly on just two Intelligences verbal/linguistic and logical/mathematical where teachers essentially teach, to reinforce and reward these intelligences. Campbell (1997) makes the point that restricting educational programmers to a focus on linguistic and mathematical intelligences minimizes the importance of other forms of knowing, and those students who fail to demonstrate the traditional academic intelligences are held in low self-esteem and their strengths may remain unrealized and lost to both the institution and society at large.

In fact, despite the efforts paid to improve the EFL textbooks, there is widespread dissatisfaction among the Algerian supervisors about the students' achievements levels in general and their learning styles in particular. Specialists believe that any EFL textbook should include enough activities that meet students' differences and promote different learning styles and various intelligences suggested by MIT. This study is an attempt to find out the extent to which My Book of English for the first middle school incorporate the MIT using content analysis. It tries to answer the following question:

To what extent does the English textbook of the first middle school incorporate the principles of the MIT ?

Methods

To satisfy the objectives of the paper, the researcher used quantitative analysis to describe and analyze the occurring of the textbook activities in relation to MIT. In this regard, 'My Book of English', a textbook of the first grade of middle school was used as data. A content analysis research tool was conducted to find out Gardner's eleven intelligences in 130 activities of the book. The intelligences are: verbal/linguistic, logical/mathematical, spatial/visual, bodily/kinesthetic, musical/rhythmic, interpersonal, intrapersonal, naturalist, moral, spiritual and existential.

Results

The question of the study was: 'to what extent does the first-year middle school textbook EFL curriculum incorporate the principles of the MIT?'

To answer this question, the researcher analyzed the content of the student's textbook of the first grade, where the activity was the unit of analysis and the intelligence was the category of analysis. The frequency of the MIT in the activities was handled as follows:

Table 2. *Frequencies of the MIT in the textbook of the first year middle school (My English Book)*

Dimension	Frequencies	Percentages
Verbal/linguistic	130	100 %
Logical/mathematical	101	77.6 %

Visual/spatial	117	90 %
Bodily/kinesthetic	54	41.53 %
Naturalist	11	8.46 %
Musical	8	6.15 %
Interpersonal	17	13.03 %
Intrapersonal	109	83.84 %
Moral	0	0.0 %
Spiritual	0	0.0 %
Existential	0	0.0 %

Table two shows the following results:

The CA results showed that the moral, existential and spiritual intelligences were not incorporated in the activities of the textbooks under study.

The verbal/linguistic, logical /mathematical, visual/spatial and intrapersonal intelligences were dominant since their percentages exceeded 50%; meanwhile, the other intelligences were not dominant since their percentages were less than 50%. The intelligences were presented in the textbooks in the following order according to their inclusion: verbal/linguistic, visual/spatial, intrapersonal and logical-mathematical.

Discussion

It should be clear right from the beginning that although the document of the general guidelines and specific outcomes for the Algerian English Language Curriculum tried to incorporate the various recent teaching and learning theories and approaches, no reference was made to the MIT. Gardner's introduction of the MIT in 1983 has generated considerable interest in the educational community and has been enthusiastically received by many educators. Kallenbach and Viens (2001) noticed that the MIT has been received by many educators because it supports pedagogy and approaches such as whole language and cooperative learning. Therefore, many individuals revised their educational practices in light of this new theory.

The English language textbook for the Algerian curriculum which was developed many times to improve the process of learning English as a foreign language was expected to be refined and updated in light of such new trends. For example, the latest update in the academic year 2006.

Only eight intelligences out of eleven appeared in the textbook under study. The moral, spiritual and existential intelligences were not incorporated in the activities of the textbook. The non-existence of the moral and spiritual intelligences in the activities could be a result of concentrating on the language itself rather than the values of the language. Probably the authors saw that learning Arabic/Islamic ideals and beliefs is the main purpose of other modules such as the module of the Arabic language, history or the module of the Islamic culture. On the other hand, the purpose of the English language module is to learn the language only. However, as learners of the language, the Algerian students should be able, at a certain level of proficiency, to talk about their values and heritage.

Moreover, the existential intelligence absence from the activities could be attributed to the fact that it deals with controversial or philosophical issues that are not suitable to a student's age or level of proficiency at this stage. This result agrees with Bothelho (2003) who explains the low percentage of the occurrences of existential intelligence in his study by saying that it deals with complex areas of study like philosophy, religions and mysticism.

In general, the inclusion of MI in the textbooks lacks balance, this could be explained by the idea that the Algerian EFL curriculum was not designed to incorporate or implement the MIT principles. The same results were obtained by Bothelho (2003) concerning the analyzed EFL and ESL textbooks taught in the Brazilian context.

The verbal/linguistic intelligence was dominant in the textbook under study; this intelligence was present in all the activities of the textbook. The importance given here to this intelligence is an expected and explainable result since language textbook usually integrates reading, writing, speaking and listening skills that depend mainly on this intelligence. Developing students' linguistic competence is the main aim of teaching a foreign language. This aim cannot be achieved or fulfilled without paying great attention to verbal/linguistic intelligence. It is worth mentioning, that the same activity could meet more than one intelligence.

Furthermore, the spatial/visual intelligence also exists with a high percentage of 90%, this is due to dealing with foreign language textbooks that depend heavily on pictures and photographs to illustrate presented situations like dialogues, reading texts, listening activities or vocabularies especially at early stages and young ages where the learners 'linguistic competence is not developed yet. Bothelho (2003) agrees that 'more visual input so offered to young and beginner learners.

The results also revealed that intrapersonal intelligence exists with a high percentage; this intelligence appeared in the activities that required tasks with individual elements like doing things by oneself, reflecting, talking about oneself and giving personal opinions. Probably, the large number of activities that are aimed at intrapersonal intelligence stems from the rational reason behind learning EFL. According to Bothelho (2003), students are encouraged to use the language in authentic real-life situations to be able to express and understand themselves, their strengths, weaknesses, moods, desires and intentions.

The logical/mathematical intelligence was dominant in the textbook understudy after the intrapersonal intelligence. Students at this early stage of learning a foreign language need to employ their minds and thoughts, to explore and discover by their own thinking.

After this intelligence, we find the bodily/kinesthetic and interpersonal intelligences. Bas (2008) agrees that younger learners tend to need more physical activities. Those students need to learn by doing, they usually get bored and lose interest after a short time; that's why physical activities are needed to keep the students attached to learning. Learning through interaction with others can be achieved by activating interpersonal intelligence. Students at this early stage of learning the foreign language need a model to imitate, interact with and get feedback from.

The musical/rhythmic and natural intelligences were not dominant at the level of the textbook. Bothelho (2003) found that musical/rhythmic intelligence was among the

less common intelligences in his study. The distribution of this intelligence was not balanced at all. This intelligence could be used to strengthen the verbal/linguistic intelligence at this learning stage because it is important for learners who are sensitive to rhythm, pitch and melody.

Conclusion

The present study arrived at the following conclusions:

Although the minister of education tried to incorporate the various recent teaching and learning theories and approaches, no reference was made to MIT. Teachers in Algeria are still far from knowing and applying the principles of MIT as well as the curriculum where psycholinguistics is almost excluded.

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